

Comparing different propulsion configurations for low-speed ship maneuvering: a system-based approach

Federico Franciosa^{1,*}, Changmin Son¹ and Stefano Brizzolara¹

¹ Virginia Tech, Blacksburg, VA, USA

Abstract. Controlled Pitch Propellers (CPPs), despite their lower efficiency and greater mechanical complexity compared to Fixed Pitch Propellers (FPPs), offer significant advantages in rapid response time, which is critical during complex maneuvers. These benefits are particularly relevant for low-speed operations in twin-shaft large ships, such as docking or undocking in confined waters. This study presents a first attempt to compare various propulsion configurations for a naval vessel, specifically the DTMB 5415 model, with the goal of identifying the optimal solution in terms of responsiveness and safety. A low-speed, system-based maneuvering simulator was developed for this purpose.

System-based maneuvering simulators are widely used in marine applications due to their ability to deliver real-time or faster-than-real-time results. Traditionally, hull forces are approximated using expansions around nonzero speeds, with hydrodynamic coefficients derived from captive model tests. While extensive research exists for cruise-speed maneuvering, the unique challenges of low-speed twin-shaft operations, characterized by strong nonlinearities, remain less explored. Most studies addressing this regime rely on high-fidelity CFD methods, such as Unsteady Reynolds-Averaged Navier-Stokes (URANS) simulations, which require considerable computational resources and time.

Here, a simplified mathematical model based on the Maneuvering Mathematical Group (MMG) approach is employed to simulate different propulsion configurations, including CPPs and FPPs. While preliminary results offer insights into key trade-offs and trends, further validation against experimental or high-fidelity numerical data is needed to fully confirm the findings.

Key words: Maneuvering, Unberthing, MMG, Low-speed

1. Introduction

In-harbor maneuvering is among the leading causes of marine accidents worldwide, accounting for as much as 51.7% of all reported incidents [1]. This highlights the importance of maneuvering performance in ship design and the growing need for solutions that enhance controllability in constrained waters. These solutions include both hydrodynamic improvements, such as advanced propulsor designs, and new control strategies for both manned and unmanned vessels. Examples of the latter include computer-based decision support systems [2], autonomous controllers [3, 4], and integrated visual-acoustic aids [5].

In addition to control strategies, physical modifications to maneuvering hardware are being explored. For instance, the VecTwin rudder [6] has shown significant improvements for single-shaft ships, especially in low-speed conditions. Another notable improvement is the use of Controllable Pitch Propellers (CPPs), which enable rapid thrust variation and directional reversals. This makes them particularly well-suited for maneuvering in narrow waters [7].

This paper investigates the performance benefits of a twin-shaft controllable pitch propeller (CPP) configuration in comparison with a fixed pitch propeller (FPP) arrangement, employing a system-based maneuvering simulator. The study demonstrates the capability of such a simulator to provide a preliminary assessment of alternative design options and control strategies at an early stage of the design process.

The maneuvering model is formulated within the MMG framework and has been extended to operate under off-design conditions, including reversing, stopping, and starting maneuvers. The effects of differential thrust - commonly employed in twin-shaft ship operations - are explicitly represented. Furthermore, the

*Correspondence to: ffranciosa@vt.edu

Figure 1. Geometry of the DTMB-5415M.

rudder model has been enhanced to account for large angles of attack (exceeding $> 90^\circ$). Such a simulator can improve the predictive capability of maneuvering assessments in port operations and may also serve as a foundation within a reinforcement learning framework for autonomous berthing and unberthing.

1.1. State of the Art

The MMG (Modular Mathematical Group) model originated in Japan during the 1970s as a structured approach to ship maneuvering prediction, based on modular hydrodynamic forces acting on the hull, propeller, and rudder. The earliest formal MMG formulation emerged from cooperative research efforts involving the Ship Research Institute (now part of NMRI) and Japanese universities and shipbuilders. The model gained traction for its ability to represent complex maneuvers - such as turning circles and zigzags - using a simplified force decomposition and experimentally derived coefficients. Over time, MMG has been extended to include twin-screw, twin-rudder, and shallow-water configurations, and has become a standard framework for maneuvering predictions, both in academia and industry [8].

While many simulation techniques are suitable for predicting ship behavior at cruising speed, low-speed maneuvering presents unique challenges. These include stronger crossflow effects and increased difficulty in experimental validation. One of the earliest low-speed maneuvering models was introduced in [9], based on the MMG framework.

Since then, a variety of modeling approaches have been developed, including unsteady RANS simulations [10], neural networks [11], and machine learning techniques [12]. Among these, the MMG model remains popular due to its computational efficiency, although it trades off some accuracy. This makes it particularly useful for early-stage design studies and sensitivity analyses.

Several relevant applications of MMG-based modeling include the equivalent rudder method for twin-rudder ships [13], and CPP maneuvering models as in [14]. Other recent proposals can be found in [15] and [16], [17] which further extend the framework to cover complex propulsion and control configurations.

2. Ship model

The vessel selected for this study is the full-scale DTMB-5415M, an open-source hull form based on the U.S. Navy's Arleigh Burke-class DDG-51 destroyer. The model, illustrated in Fig. 1., is fully appended and includes a sonar dome, bilge keels, a skeg, and a transom stern. Its principal dimensions are summarized in Table 1. As shown, the DTMB-5415M features a twin-shaft, twin-rudder configuration, which makes it well-suited for evaluating propulsion control strategies and maneuvering performance at low speeds.

This particular hull has been the subject of numerous international benchmark studies, including the SIMMAN (Ship Maneuvering) workshops [18], and is widely used as a reference geometry for both experimental and numerical investigations involving ship resistance, propulsion, and maneuvering. It has been extensively analyzed using CFD methods to evaluate flow behavior, propeller-rudder interactions, and to validate system-based maneuvering models. Notable contributions include the studies presented in [19], [20], [21], and [22].

Table 1. Ship and Rudder Parameters

Symbol	Value
L_{pp}	142 m
L_{wl}	142.18 m
B_{wl}	19.06 m
T	6.15 m
∇	8424.4 m ³
S	2972.6 m ²
C_b	0.5155
x_g	-0.652 % L_{pp} aft
AR	1.26
A_{rudder}	15.4 m ²
U_{ship}	4.63 m/s
J_z	1.09×10^{10} kg · m ²

3. Mathematical Model

The simulator is based on the traditional MMG (Modular Mathematical Group) model, with several adaptations that enable the simulation of off-design operating conditions. The body-fixed coordinate system is defined as follows: the x -axis is positive forward, the y -axis is positive to starboard, and the z -axis is positive downward. The origin of the reference frame is located at midships.

3.1. Equations of Motion

The equations of motion are formulated as implemented in the simulator, with acceleration terms on the left-hand side and Coriolis and external forces on the right-hand side:

$$(M - X_{\dot{u}})\dot{u} = X + Mvr + Mx_G r^2 \quad (1)$$

$$(M - Y_{\dot{v}})\dot{v} + (M - Y_{\dot{r}})\dot{r} = Y + Mx_G ur \quad (2)$$

$$(I_z - N_{\dot{r}})\dot{r} + (Mx_G - N_{\dot{v}})\dot{v} = N - Mx_G ur \quad (3)$$

Here, M is the ship mass, x_G is the longitudinal position of the center of gravity relative to the body-fixed frame, and I_z is the moment of inertia about the vertical axis. The variables u , v , and r represent the surge, sway, and yaw velocities, respectively. The coefficients $X_{\dot{u}}$, $Y_{\dot{v}}$, $Y_{\dot{r}}$, $N_{\dot{v}}$, and $N_{\dot{r}}$ are the added mass terms (note that these are typically negative).

The total external forces and moments are given by:

$$X = X_H + X_R + X_P \quad (4)$$

$$Y = Y_H + Y_R + Y_P \quad (5)$$

$$N = N_H + N_R + N_P \quad (6)$$

In the MMG notation, the subscripts H , R , and P refer to the contributions from the hull, rudder, and propeller, respectively.

Table 2. Hydrodynamic Derivatives at $Fn = 0.25$

Coefficient	Value	Coefficient	Value	Coefficient	Value
X_{vv}	-0.0427	Y_v	-0.2673	N_v	-0.1351
X_{rr}	-0.0090	Y_{vvv}	-1.7940	N_{vvv}	-0.2866
X_{vr}	0.0300	Y_r	-0.0313	N_r	-0.0372
X_{vvv}	-0.0903	Y_{rrr}	-0.0454	N_{rrr}	-0.0255
X_{rru}	-0.0094	Y_{vrr}	-1.3683	N_{vrr}	-0.4011
		Y_{rvv}	-1.7067	N_{rvv}	-0.5512
		Y_{vu}	-0.0242	N_{vu}	-0.0397
		Y_{vuu}	0.0794	N_{vuu}	0.0294
		Y_{ru}	-0.0265	N_{ru}	-0.0208
		Y_{ruu}	0.0033	N_{ruu}	0.0034

3.2. Hull Forces

The hydrodynamic forces due to the hull in all three degrees of freedom are modeled using a set of hydrodynamic derivatives obtained from [23]. Most of these derivatives are speed-dependent, which introduces additional uncertainty into the model. To address this, an interpolation method between multiple sets of coefficients is currently being developed. For the present study, the coefficients corresponding to the tested speed ($Fn = 0.25$) are used and summarized in Table 2.

The resistance force is derived directly from towing tank experiments [24] and scaled according to the ITTC standard procedure [25]. For reverse speeds, the resistance is conservatively increased by 25%.

Added masses are estimated using empirical and statistical approaches. The surge added mass, given in Equation 7, is taken from [26], which refers back to the formulation by [27]. The remaining terms are based on [16], which also uses Clarke's original empirical formulations.

$$X_{\dot{u}} = M \cdot 0.05 \quad (7)$$

$$Y_{\dot{v}} = 0.108 \cdot (0.5 \cdot \rho \cdot L_{pp}^2 \cdot T) \quad (8)$$

$$Y_{\dot{r}} = 0.5 \cdot \rho \cdot L_{wl}^4 \cdot \left[-\pi \cdot \left(\frac{T}{L_{wl}} \right)^2 \cdot \left(0.67 \cdot \frac{B_{wl}}{L_{wl}} - 0.0033 \cdot \left(\frac{B_{wl}}{L_{wl}} \right)^2 \right) \right] \quad (9)$$

$$N_{\dot{v}} = Y_{\dot{v}} \quad (10)$$

$$N_{\dot{r}} = 0.5 \cdot \rho \cdot L_{wl}^5 \cdot \left[-\pi \cdot \left(\frac{T}{L_{wl}} \right)^2 \cdot \left(0.0833 + 0.017 \cdot \frac{C_b B_{wl}}{T} - 0.033 \cdot \frac{B_{wl}}{L_{wl}} \right) \right] \quad (11)$$

3.3. Propeller Model

FPP Propeller Model A five-bladed Wageningen B-series propeller [28] is used in this study as the fixed pitch propeller (FPP), differing from the original propeller specified in the SIMMAN benchmark [18]. The rotation rate is adjusted to match the required ship speed. This substitution is necessary due to the lack of four-quadrant open-water data for the SIMMAN propeller, which are essential for modeling off-design conditions.

The inflow angle β , thrust coefficient C_T^* , and torque coefficient C_Q^* are defined as:

$$\beta = \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{V_a}{0.7\pi n D} \right) \quad (12)$$

$$C_T^* = \frac{T}{\left(\frac{\pi}{8} \right) \rho [V_a^2 + (0.7\pi n D)^2] D^2} \quad (13)$$

Figure 2. Q-factor during a puew sway CFD simulation.

$$C_Q^* = \frac{Q}{\left(\frac{\pi}{8}\right) \rho [V_a^2 + (0.7\pi n D)^2] D^3} \quad (14)$$

In these expressions, D is the propeller diameter, n is the rotational speed in revolutions per second, ρ is the fluid density, and V_a is the advance velocity, defined as:

$$V_a = u (1 - w_P(\beta_P)) \quad (15)$$

The hull's influence is included through the wake fraction w_P , modeled here as a function of the local drift angle at the propeller β_P . This correction is applied independently to port and starboard propellers using CFD data from [29]. An Unsteady-RANS simulation campaign has been carried out on a similar hull. This included steady drift, pure sway, and pure yaw tests. Several turbulent phenomena affect the flow at the propeller disks, which greatly influence propulsive capabilities. Examples are vortex structures originating from the bilge keel and from the skeg, shown in Figure 2..

The resulting thrust is then dimensionalized and scaled using the thrust deduction factor $1 - t$.

CPP Propeller Model For the controllable pitch propeller (CPP), a two-quadrant model is implemented. The open-water characteristics were provided by Rolls-Royce Naval Marine. While the CPP has the same diameter as the FPP, its pitch-to-diameter ratio P/D is allowed to vary between -1.2 and 1.2 .

During the maneuver, the propeller shaft speed n is kept constant, and thrust is regulated by adjusting the blade pitch. This is justified by the assumption that pitch dynamics are significantly faster than rotational dynamics. Further details are discussed in the section on the unberthing maneuver.

3.4. Rudder model

The rudder model is based on [30], since lift and drag curves are not available.

$$\frac{dC_L}{d\alpha} = \frac{a_0 a_e}{\cos(\Omega) \left(\frac{a_e^2}{\cos^4(\Omega)} + 4 \right)^{1/2} + \frac{57.3 a_0}{\pi}} \quad (16)$$

The terms are hereby summarized:

- a_e is the effective aspect ratio, given by

$$a_e = K_i b^2 / Ar$$

where K_i is the increase of aspect ratio due to image effect, b is the span, Ar is the planform area, $a_0 = 0.9 \cdot 2 \cdot \pi$

- Ω is the quarter chord sweep angle.

Figure 3. Trajectories of the turning circle maneuver from the maneuvering simulator (red line) and the experimental results (black line).

The angle α is the effective inflow angle at the rudder, which is explained in equation 17. The angle is limited to a range of -17° to 17° to simulate a stalling effect, as suggested in [31].

$$\alpha = \delta - \gamma \arctan\left(\frac{v - x_R r}{u}\right) \quad (17)$$

where δ is the rudder angle, γ is a straightening coefficient, and x_R is the longitudinal rudder location.

The velocity at the rudder is considered to be accelerated by the propeller. Here, the classical formulation [26] has been slightly modified to include negative thrust and velocity, resulting in equation 18.

$$u_R = \epsilon \sqrt{\eta \left\{ V_A + \kappa \left(\sqrt{V_A^2 + \frac{8T}{\pi \rho D^2}} - V_A \right) \right\}^2 + V_A^2 (1 - \eta)} \quad (18)$$

The sign of u_R has been assumed in accordance with the direction of the thrust.

4. Results

As no free-running model tests are currently available for the unberthing maneuver, the simulation results are compared against free-running tests performed at FORCE, as reported in [26]. The comparison shows good agreement overall, although final validation must eventually be conducted against actual unberthing trials using free-running models.

4.1. Turning Circle

The trajectory of the turning circle maneuver, shown in Fig. 3., demonstrates good agreement with experimental data. However, the initial lateral (y) displacement is slightly overestimated by the simulator. This discrepancy may indicate that the cross-flow terms in the mathematical model do not fully capture transient hydrodynamic effects, which are particularly significant during unsteady maneuvers like unberthing.

The yaw velocity r , presented in Fig. 4., is slightly underestimated overall, with the simulation exhibiting a sharper peak than observed in the experiments. This overprediction is consistent with similar findings reported in [26] and appears to be a known limitation of simplified maneuvering models. Nevertheless, the initial slope and trend align well with experimental observations.

Figure 4. Yaw velocity of the turning circle maneuver from the maneuvering simulator (red line) and the experimental results (black line).

The absolute velocity time history, shown in Fig. 5., is slightly underestimated by the simulation. The model reaches a steady-state velocity after approximately 150 seconds but fails to capture the fluctuations observed in the experimental data. It is important to note that the simulated maneuver starts from rest.

4.2. Zigzag Maneuver

A $20^\circ/20^\circ$ zigzag maneuver is conducted to assess the model's ability to capture unsteady effects. As shown in Figs. 6. and 7., the overshoot angle is well predicted; however, the overall maneuver is executed more quickly in the simulation than in the experimental results. In particular, the system-based simulator triggers the second and third rudder deflections earlier than in the experiment, which leads to a mismatch in the resulting trajectory and heading evolution.

4.3. Unberthing

An unberthing maneuver was simulated using the developed system-based maneuvering simulator to assess and compare the performance of different propulsion configurations. The maneuver begins with the ship positioned parallel and close to a pier wall and ends with the ship still parallel to the pier but laterally displaced away from it, maintaining approximately the same longitudinal (x) position. This trajectory is executed identically for both the Fixed Pitch Propeller (FPP) and Controllable Pitch Propeller (CPP) configurations.

The maneuver is structured in multiple phases. In the initial phase, the rudders are turned toward the pier to generate lateral lift, which begins to move the stern away from the pier. This rudder deflection is essential for producing lateral motion. Accurate modeling of the local flow acceleration over the rudders is critical during this phase. Without this effect, the induced rudder forces would be unrealistically weak, as they would depend solely on the very low surge velocity typical in the early stages of unberthing.

Once a target yaw angle - here set to $\psi = 10^\circ$ is reached, the thrust is reversed to stop the vessel's rotation and forward motion. In the FPP case, this requires halting and reversing the shaft rotation, introducing a time delay, here assumed to be 5 s, while in the CPP configuration, the same is achieved instantaneously by varying the blade pitch. Following this, the vessel continues to rotate and translate away from the pier in astern motion, before being stopped once more. Finally, forward thrust is reapplied, and differential thrust between the port and starboard propellers is used to straighten the ship's heading while preserving the lateral offset gained during the previous phases.

Figure 5. Absolute velocity of the turning circle maneuver from the maneuvering simulator (red line) and the experimental results (black line).

Figure 6. Trajectories of the $20^\circ/20^\circ$ zigzag maneuver from the maneuvering simulator (red line) and the experimental results (black line).

Figure 7. Rudder deflection time history during the $20^\circ/20^\circ$ zigzag maneuver from the maneuvering simulator (red line) and the experimental results (black line).

This sequence is representative of a common low-speed harbor maneuver.

As shown in Figures 8. and 9., the maneuver performed with the FPP configuration lasts approximately 240 seconds. The final position is not perfectly parallel to the initial heading, with a deviation of about 10 degrees, although the vessel returns to roughly the same x coordinate as it started from.

In contrast, the CPP maneuver - illustrated in Figures 10. and 11. - results in a greater final x displacement but, at the same time, achieves a greater y displacement. These outcomes can be further refined through more systematic control strategies, such as implementing PID controllers or incorporating expert input from professional ship operators.

Notably, the CPP maneuver completes the operation approximately 15 seconds faster than the FPP configuration.

5. Conclusions

This study presents a comparative analysis of two propulsion configurations for the twin-shaft ship DTMB-5415M: one equipped with Fixed Pitch Propellers (FPPs) and the other with Controllable Pitch Propellers (CPPs). A modified fast-time MMG-based maneuvering simulator is used to model the same unberthing maneuver for both configurations. The simulator accounts for differential thrust, propeller-induced flow acceleration at the rudders, reverse thrust capabilities, and incorporates a four-quadrant representation of propeller behavior.

Performance is assessed based on the execution of the unberthing maneuver, for which no experimental validation data are currently available. As such, the method remains subject to further validation. Results indicate that the CPP configuration offers significant advantages in terms of maneuverability and safety. Its rapid response and ability to reverse thrust without altering RPMs allow for smoother and more controlled maneuvering. In contrast, the FPP setup is hindered by delays inherent to reversing shaft rotation, resulting in less responsive behavior during critical phases of the maneuver.

The system-based maneuvering simulator provides a fast and practical tool for performing such comparative studies. However, it lacks validation under low-speed and off-design conditions. Several modeling simplifications limit the accuracy of the results, which should therefore be interpreted as indicative rather than definitive. Future work will focus on validating the model using free-running experiments and full scale data (to identify scaling factors), incorporating additional effects such as shallow water dynamics and

Figure 8. Trajectory of an unberthing maneuver performed with FPP propellers.

Figure 9. Time histories of the rudder angle and the RPMs of an unberthing maneuver performed with FPP propellers.

Figure 10. Trajectory of an unberthing maneuver performed with CPP propellers.

Figure 11. Time histories of the rudder angle and the P/D s of an unberthing maneuver performed with CPP propellers.

a more refined four-quadrant rudder model, and developing a coupled dynamic representation of the entire propulsion system, including motor and shaft behavior.

Acknowledgments

The authors would like to acknowledge Rolls-Royce Naval Marine for their support and for providing the controllable pitch propeller (CPP) data used in this study. The authors also extend their gratitude to MARIN for supplying experimental data, which served as a valuable reference for model validation.

References

- [1] European Maritime Safety Agency. Annual overview of marine casualties and incidents 2023. 2024.
- [2] Kuniji Kose, Junji Fukudo, Kenji Sugano, Shigeru Akagi, and Mihoko Harada. On a computer aided maneuvering system in harbours. *Journal of the Society of Naval Architects of Japan*, 1986, 1986.
- [3] Angelo Alessandri, Silvia Donnarumma, Michele Martelli, and Stefano Vignolo. Motion control for autonomous navigation in blue and narrow waters using switched controllers. *Journal of Marine Science and Engineering*, 7, 2019.
- [4] Hakon Hagen Helgesen, Torbjorn Fuglestad, Krzysztof Cisek, Bjornar Vik, Oivind Kare Kjerstad, and Tor Arne Johansen. Inertial navigation aided by ultra-wideband ranging for ship docking and harbor maneuvering. *IEEE Journal of Oceanic Engineering*, 48, 2023.
- [5] Øystein Volden, David Cabecinhas, António Pascoal, and Thor I. Fossen. Development and experimental evaluation of visual-acoustic navigation for safe maneuvering of unmanned surface vehicles in harbor and waterway areas. *Ocean Engineering*, 280, 2023.
- [6] Hironori YASUKAWA, Noritaka HIRATA, Susumu TANAKA, and Hiroki HATA. Tank tests on low speed maneuvering of a ship with vectwin rudder. *The Journal of Japan Institute of Navigation*, 124, 2011.
- [7] John S. Carlton. *Marine Propellers and Propulsion*. Butterworth-Heinemann, 4th edition, 2019.
- [8] H. Yasukawa and Y. Yoshimura. Introduction of mmg standard method for ship maneuvering predictions. *Journal of Marine Science and Technology (Japan)*, 20, 2015.
- [9] Kuniji Kose, Hiroyoshi Hinata, Yasuhisa Hashizume, and Eijiro Futagawa. On a mathematical model of maneuvering motions of ships in low speeds. *Journal of the Society of Naval Architects of Japan*, 1984, 1984.
- [10] Daejeong Kim, Jeongbin Yim, Soonseok Song, Yigit Kemal Demirel, and Tahsin Tezdogan. A systematic investigation on the manoeuvring performance of a ship performing low-speed manoeuvres in adverse weather conditions using cfd. *Ocean Engineering*, 263, 2022.
- [11] Kouki Wakita, Atsuo Maki, Naoya Umeda, Yoshiki Miyauchi, Tohga Shimoji, Dimas M. Rachman, and Youhei Akimoto. On neural network identification for low-speed ship maneuvering model. *Journal of Marine Science and Technology (Japan)*, 27, 2022.
- [12] Rasmus E. Nielsen, Dimitrios Papageorgiou, Lazaros Nalpantidis, Bugge T. Jensen, and Mogens Blanke. Machine learning enhancement of manoeuvring prediction for ship digital twin using full-scale recordings. *Ocean Engineering*, 257, 2022.
- [13] R. Okuda, H. Yasukawa, M. Sano, N. Hirata, Y. Yoshimura, Y. Furukawa, and A. Matsuda. Maneuvering simulations of twin-propeller and twin-rudder ship in shallow water using equivalent single rudder model. *Journal of Marine Science and Technology (Japan)*, 27, 2022.
- [14] Xiao Feng Sun, Yong Yin, and Xiu Feng Zhang. Maneuvering mathematical model for ships equipped with controllable pitch propeller. *Dalian Haishi Daxue Xuebao/Journal of Dalian Maritime University*, 33, 2007.
- [15] Takuya Taniguchi and Atsuo Maki. A proposal of the maneuvering motion model for low-speed operations in harbor. *Ocean Engineering*, 330:121172, 06 2025.
- [16] Ghalib Taimuri, Jerzy Matusiak, Tommi Mikkola, Pentti Kujala, and Spyros Hirdaris. A 6-dof maneuvering model for the rapid estimation of hydrodynamic actions in deep and shallow waters. *Ocean Engineering*, 218:108103, 2020.
- [17] Omotayo Oladele, William Lambert, and Stefano Brizzolara. A combined maneuvering and seakeeping model for the onr tumblehome. In *Proceedings of the International Conference on Offshore Mechanics and Arctic Engineering - OMAE*, volume 5, 2023.

- [18] Frederick Stern, K. Agdrup, S.Y. Kim, Andrés Cura-Hochbaum, Key Rhee, Frans Quadvlieg, P. Perdon, Takanori Hino, Riccardo Broglia, and J. Gorski. Experience from simman 2008—the first workshop on verification and validation of ship maneuvering simulation methods. *Journal of Ship Research*, 55:135–147, 06 2011.
- [19] Suleyman Duman and Sakir Bal. Prediction of the turning and zig zag maneuvering performance of a surface combatant with urans. *Ocean Systems Engineering*, 7, 2017.
- [20] Joe Longo and Fred Stern. Uncertainty assessment for towing tank tests with example for surface combatant dtmb model 5415. *Journal of Ship Research*, 49, 2005.
- [21] Andrea Franceschi, Benedetto Piaggio, Roberto Tonelli, Diego Villa, and Michele Viviani. Assessment of the manoeuvrability characteristics of a twin shaft naval vessel using an open-source cfd code. *Journal of Marine Science and Engineering*, 9, 2021.
- [22] Simone Mancini, Ermina Begovic, Alexander H. Day, and Atilla Incecik. Verification and validation of numerical modelling of dtmb 5415 roll decay. *Ocean Engineering*, 162, 2018.
- [23] Hyunse Yoon, Claus D. Simonsen, Lanfranco Benedetti, Joseph Longo, Yasuyuki Toda, and Frederick Stern. Benchmark cfd validation data for surface combatant 5415 in pmm maneuvers – part i: Force/moment/motion measurements. *Ocean Engineering*, 109:705–734, 2015.
- [24] A. Olivieri, F. Pistani, A. Avanzini, F. Stern, and R. Penna. Towing tank experiments of resistance, sinkage and trim, boundary layer, wake, and free surface flow around a naval combatant in sean 2340 model. Technical Report IIHR Technical Report No. 421, IIHR – Hydroscience & Engineering, The University of Iowa, Iowa City, Iowa, 2001.
- [25] Practical guidelines for ship resistance cfd. Technical Report 7.5-03-02-04, International Towing Tank Conference (ITTC), Resistance & Propulsion Committee of the 29th ITTC, 2021. Effective date: 06/2021.
- [26] Omer Faruk Sukas, Omer Kemal Kinaci, and Sakir Bal. Theoretical background and application of mansim for ship maneuvering simulations. *Ocean Engineering*, 192, 2019.
- [27] D. B. Clarke, P. Gedling, and G. Hine. The application of manoeuvring criteria in hull design using linear theory. *Transactions of the Royal Institution of Naval Architects*, pages 45–68, 1982.
- [28] G. Kuiper. The wageningen propeller series. Technical Report Publication No. 92-001, MARIN, 1992.
- [29] Federico Franciosa, Omotayo Oladele, Giuliano Vernengo, and Stefano Brizzolara. Hull wake characteristics for twin shaft ships maneuvering in calm water. In *Proceedings of the International Conference Hydrodynamics, Rome*, 2024.
- [30] L. F. Whicker and L. F. Felner. Free stream characteristics of a family of low aspect ratio control surfaces for application to ship design. Technical Report DTRC Report 933, David Taylor Research Center, 1958.
- [31] Louis Landweber. Hydrodynamic forces on a slowly maneuvering body in an ideal fluid. Technical Report NASA-TM-78560, NASA, 1977.